

"YOSH ILMIY IJODKORLAR: SHARLOTTA BRONTENING "JEYN EYRE" ASARI ASOSIDA"

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STYLISTIC FIGURES IN "JANE EYRE"

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Annotation: *This article examines the stylistic figures used in Charlotte Bronte's novel "Jane Eyre" and identifies where and how they are used, and the role they play in enhancing the artistic value of the work.*

Key words: *Distinguish, stylistic features, experiences, ideological, unrepeatable.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются стилистические фигуры, использованные в романе Шарлотты Бронте «Джейн Эйр», где и как они используются, а также их роль в повышении художественной ценности произведения.*

Ключевые слова: *Различие, стилистические особенности, переживания, идейность, неповторимость.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Sharlotta Brontening "Jeyn Eyr" romanida qo'llanilgan stilistik figuralar ko'rib chiqilib, ularning qayerda va qanday qo'llangani, asarning badiiy qiymatini oshirishda tutgan o'rni aniqlanadi.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *Farq, uslubiy xususiyatlar, kechinmalar, mafkura, o'ziga xoslik.*

Syntactic-stylistic figures are intonation-syntactic methods that create expressiveness in fiction and perform a certain stylistic function. Syntactic-stylistic figures consist of special syntactic turns that help increase the emotionality of speech, and include parallelism, repetition and its types, antithesis, inversion, ellipsis, gradation, etc. Although these devices were initially considered figures specific to poetic speech, they began to be studied as a phenomenon of prosaic speech in later published linguistic literature. Stylistic figures make speech impressive and attractive, and also provide an opportunity to quickly and easily convey ideas to the listener. The speech forms created with their help tend to be sonorous.

One of the scholars who skillfully used stylistic figures in her work is Charlotte Bronte. Charlotte Brontë's novel "Jane Eyre" was published in 1847 and became an instant hit. The role of women in society and increasing their social activity has always been a topical issue. Consequently, the image of a woman in the field of world literature plays an important role with its unparalleled aspects. It should be noted that the creation of the image of a woman indicates that she is a part of society.[2]

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Problems related to women and society in world literature have been explored in the novels of Jane Austen, Charles Dickens, and Mary Roberts[3]It is not only a love story, but also a deeply social novel that covers psychological themes , but also distinguished by its own stylistic style. On addition this, Charlotte Bronte did establish her reputation as a writer through the novel Jane Eyre which really reflects the women voice for their role in the society having equal rights to men. Literary world of Bronte is revealed by the reading list she made up for her friend Ellen Nosey in a letter dated July 4, 1837 . Adrienne Rich: Rich analyzes "Jane Eyre" from a feminist perspective, exploring Jane's struggle to maintain her independence and identity. She sees Jane as a symbol that reflects the difficulties women face in a patriarchal society. Elaine Showalter: In A Literature of Their Own, Showalter analyzes Jane Eyre in terms of the development of literature written by women writers. She sees Jane as a female protagonist trying to find her place in an era when women were seeking to have their own voices and tell their own stories.

This was the reason for the comparison with the great proponent of romanticism, Byron, during discussions about the work of Charlotte Bronte and her heroines (especially Jane Eyre). In particular, a major English literary critic of the mid-20th century, W. Allen, expressed himself on this score, believing that Charlotte's novel is "a female response to Byron and his Byronic hero." [4] 'The role of women in society and increasing their social activity has always been a topical issue'. 'The stylistic figures used in the work serve to enhance the overall impact of the novel, increase its artistic value, and express the inner experiences of the characters more vividly and clearly. Below we will dwell in detail on the stylistic features of the novel with examples. Charlotte Bronte used the following stylistic figures in her work: Simile, litota, metaphora, symbolism hyperole, antithesis, understatement, rhetorical questions, oxymoron, allusion, gradation, imagery, alleteration, irony, repetition, personification, euphemism, archaism, metonymya paradox, foreshadowing, anaphora, epithet, parallelism, proverb.

Metaphor and simile: Charlotte Bronte uses metaphors and similes as stylistic figures to more vividly describe the inner state, feelings, and experiences of the characters in her work. For example, Jane's childhood loneliness and fear are likened to "a small boat sailing on a dark sea." This simile vividly describes Jane's loneliness, weakness, and vulnerability.

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Hyperbole and Litote: In this work, the writer uses hyperbole to exaggerate some feelings, and litotes to understate them. For example, Rochester's wealth and position are described as being as vast as the sky and the earth through hyperbole.

Antithesis: Antithesis is used to express a contrast. For example, the difference between the social status, character, and worldview of Jane and Rochester is emphasized through antithesis.

Inversion (changing word order): Inversion is used to emphasize certain words and create a poetic tone. This technique helps Brontë create her own romantic and gothic style.

Rhetorical Questions: Rhetorical questions are used to further expand the reader's thinking and increase the impact of the work. For example, Jane often asks rhetorical questions about her fate and future.

Accomplished Charlotte's writings were highly lauded by such authors as William Makepeace Thackeray, and has since inspired numerous adaptations for television and film, and numerous other author's works including Jean Rhys' 'prequel' Wide Sargasso Sea.[5]

The stylistic figures listed above make "Jane Eyre" more impressive and at the same time increase its artistic value. Brontë's skillful use of stylistic figures serves to reveal the ideological content of the work more deeply, to make the reader want to read more and to leave an unforgettable, unrepeatable impression on the reader.

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